

UK SPACE ACTIVITIES 2002

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DIRECTOR GENERAL'S INTRODUCTION

IT GIVES ME GREAT PLEASURE TO INTRODUCE THIS YEAR'S EDITION OF UK SPACE ACTIVITIES. THIS IS OUR ANNUAL PUBLICATION, PRESENTING BNSC AND FOCUSING ON THE SPECIFIC EVENTS AND ACTIVITIES THAT HAVE OCCUPIED US OVER THE PAST FINANCIAL YEAR.

Since the last edition was published in May 2001, there have been a number of significant events which have strengthened the UK's position at the forefront of space technology and its development. This publication highlights the huge variety of space activity in the UK, demonstrating the role of BNSC in promoting both an innovative and successful commercial sector, and a world class scientific community.

It has been an exciting year for European space as a whole, and the UK has played a major role in a number of European successes. In November, the UK hosted the European Space Agency's Ministerial Council in Edinburgh, which endorsed further international cooperation between ESA and the European Union. This coordination of activity is strongly supported by the UK and builds on an initiative taken at the previous Ministerial Council.

You will read in these pages about the major achievements of the past year, such as the launch of Envisat, ESA's Earth observation satellite of unprecedented ambition and technological

innovation. There is also the potential for ground-breaking developments in the next stage of Galileo, the joint satellite navigation project of ESA and the EU. BNSC supports those and other ventures at European level. BNSC also supports, at the national level, the development of smaller scale applications and satellites under the S@TCOM and MOSAIC programmes. We recognise the huge potential benefits from innovative approaches both in research and in addressing the expanding applications markets.

However, we recognise that the potential benefits of space activity are not obvious to all, and so we are also working hard to communicate the results of our activity to the public. To this end we supported the opening of the National Space Science Centre in Leicester, which will help to both inform and inspire our young people about space. We are also steadily expanding our own website, <http://www.bnsc.gov.uk>

Through its partners, BNSC works to assist the UK space sector to achieve ever greater success in all areas of scientific research, technology development and downstream application development, in order to make space work for the benefit of all citizens in practical and tangible ways. This publication highlights some of the many opportunities that we are currently exploiting.

Director General
Dr Colin Hicks

WELCOME TO BNSC

BNSC, THE BRITISH NATIONAL SPACE CENTRE, ACTS AS THE UK'S OWN 'SPACE AGENCY'.

It was formed in 1985 with the specific purpose of helping Britain get the best scientific and economic value out of national and international activities in space. It has an important role to play in the development of space technologies and their application, and provides UK scientific and industrial communities with a single voice on the international arena. It also promotes the transfer of relevant technologies to other areas of industry.

BNSC is a voluntary partnership of Government Departments and Research Councils with an interest in the development or exploitation of space technologies. By working with industry and academia, the partners further these interests in a good example of joined-up thinking across Government. Many of these organisations are actual users of space systems, and so are well-placed to advise on how its commercial potential can be developed most effectively.

BNSC is also a founder member of the European Space Agency (ESA), and around 60 per cent of UK civil space expenditure is channelled through ESA. BNSC works closely with ESA, the European Union, as well as its international partners, to further its activities in space.

Currently, the partners' combined expenditure on civil space amounts to around £180 million per year. Naturally, BNSC is keen to operate in the most efficient way. With this aim, it undergoes regular reviews of its activities and how they are conducted. Following the House of Commons Trade and Industry Report published in July 2000 and the Government's response to its findings, a Review of BNSC was conducted during 2001. This is expected to recommend some changes which will increase the responsibility of the Research Councils for delivering success in the ESA programmes of scientific research. The recent reorganisation within DTI has seen BNSC move into the newly created Innovation Group, with whose objectives BNSC's aims have long been aligned.

01

MAJOR EVENTS OF 2001/2002

Over the last year, BNSC made major new commitments totalling over £381m to put space to work in many different areas. The UK hosted ESA's Ministerial Council in November 2001 in Edinburgh, where many important decisions were made about new space programmes. A decade of investment and development culminated in the successful launch of Envisat, the most complex Earth observation satellite ever built.

UK Space Minister Lord Sainsbury hosted ESA's Ministerial Council, which took place in Edinburgh on 14th-15th November 2001. This meeting of the Ministers responsible for space affairs in the 15 ESA Member States and Canada, which takes place every few years, is one of the most significant events on the space calendar. It sets the strategic direction for the Agency, commits to new initiatives and endorses the next stages in ESA's on-going programmes. The decisions made by the Ministerial Council help to keep Europe at the forefront of space science and technology.

One of the key policy decisions was to forge closer links with the European Union, with the ultimate aim

of implementing a truly European space policy in order to further ESA's aim of putting space at the service of the European citizen.

At the meeting, Ministers discussed proposals for the European civil satellite navigation system, Galileo: a joint project between ESA and the European Union. ESA Member States subscribed, subject to the decision of the EU Transport Council. In the intervening months, the UK worked hard within ESA and the EU to secure satisfactory financial and management arrangements that would improve the efficiency and cost effectiveness of the project. Galileo was finally given the go-ahead at a meeting of EU Transport Ministers on 26th March 2002.

1. Hundreds of new services will result from Galileo global navigation system, which was given the go-ahead in March 2002. The Galileo system is due to come into operation by 2008 (Image: ESA).

Galileo should be operational by 2008 and will provide an accurate, secure and certified satellite positioning system that has many applications in road, rail, air and maritime traffic control, and could create many new jobs in the UK.

Ministers also gave a strong commitment to the Global Monitoring for Environment and Security (GMES) initiative. GMES focuses on improving the use of Europe's existing and planned Earth observation systems in order to help us manage our natural resources. The first meeting of the GMES Steering Committee took place in Brussels in March 2002, and it is hoped that a European global monitoring service will be operational by 2008.

The successful launch of Envisat, Europe's largest environmental monitoring satellite, was undoubtedly one of the past year's most significant events in space. British and European scientists and engineers have worked for 10 years to perfect the most complex

Earth observation satellite ever, with a £300 million investment by the UK. ESA's £1.4 billion satellite, a 'body scanner' designed to give a global picture of the Earth's well being, was launched from Kourou in French Guiana on 1st March 2002. Envisat is now circling the Earth once every 100 minutes and will provide scientists both here and abroad with vital information on global warming, climate change and depletion of the ozone layer.

In January 2002, Lord Sainsbury gave an update on developments in the field of Near Earth Objects (NEOs), announcing the success of the National Space Science Centre in Leicester in winning the contract to host the UK's NEO Information Centre. This opened in April 2002.

Finally, the end of December 2001 saw the retirement of Dr Paul Murdin, the Director of Space Science at BNSC, who oversaw BNSC's involvement in many important space science missions.

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1. BNSC focuses on an area with the most commercial potential, such as telecommunications (Image: Astrium). 2. Science missions are making important breakthroughs. Images from ESA's solar satellite, SOHO, give us new views of the Sun (Image: ESA).

UK SPACE POLICY

BNSC is at the forefront of significant changes taking place in science today, promoting numerous innovations in technology, as well as building on the UK's commercial success and maintaining the leading edge in space science.

A Government report, entitled 'A Science Policy for the 21st Century', states that when science applications are properly regulated and address clear human needs they win public support. Scientific research is now being carried out more productively than ever, and the results lead to products and services that benefit all society.

The UK's space policy, formulated by Government Departments and Research Councils with interests in civil space, has these aims in mind.

It contains five principal objectives that BNSC pursues in support of the Government's industrial and scientific goals:

- To help industry maximise profitable business opportunities in the development and exploitation of space systems which improve quality of life and customer choice
- To foster the development of innovative technology, its commercial exploitation and its application in research
- To pursue the highest quality astronomy and space science
- To improve our understanding of the Earth's environment and natural resources
- To communicate the results and their significance to a broad audience

The Government invests around £180 million per year in civil space technology and services. BNSC aims to achieve its objectives as cost-effectively as possible, focusing investment in areas with the greatest commercial potential, such as Earth observation, satellite communications and navigation. BNSC also promotes space science excellence, giving new information about our universe that may lead to scientific, environmental and economic advances in the future. Equally, BNSC ensures that technological developments taking place in the space industry can be shared with other industries.

With 60 per cent of the UK's civil space expenditure channelled through the European Space Agency (ESA), the UK plays a constructive role in the development of ESA's priorities.

The European Space Strategy, jointly adopted by ESA and the European Commission on 16th November 2000, signifies closer co-operation between the EU and ESA, and the UK is a strong supporter of the progress made to further this coordination.

The UK's space priorities are continuously kept under review. Every three years, a Space Strategy is developed by BNSC through consultation with its partners and industrial and scientific communities. A new Space Strategy is currently being debated and the formal consultation process will take place during Summer 2002.

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INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATIONS

BNSC works with many countries and the international community as a whole to maximise the benefits that space can bring to the world. Through collaborations with international organisations, BNSC ensures that its projects are carried out in the most economical and effective way.

BNSC firmly believes that space is an international resource, which can be utilised for the benefit of all citizens. Since its inception in 1985, BNSC has worked closely with space agencies and others overseas to develop scientific and technical expertise that is truly world class. These collaborations also serve to share the costs of space activities, facilitating ambitious and complex projects.

1. Via the Met Office, the UK contributes to the European monitoring of global weather conditions (Image: EUMETSAT from Meteosat - 7). 2. Environmental problems are of international concern. This shows the size of the ozone hole over Antarctica (Image: NASA).

By far the most significant international alliances for BNSC are within the 15-member European Space Agency (ESA). Around 60 per cent of the UK's space expenditure is channelled through ESA, which forms the cornerstone of the UK space programme. The UK plays a lead role in many of ESA's space science missions, as well as in space research, technology and applications.

BNSC is strongly supportive of closer coordination on space matters between ESA and the European Union (EU). Following the development of the Joint European Space Strategy in 2000, further progress towards this goal was given endorsement by the

unprecedented attendance of Romano Prodi, the President of the European Commission, at the ESA Ministerial Council in Edinburgh. This commitment to coordination is now being taken forward by both ESA and the EU, with first steps towards negotiating a framework agreement for activity currently underway.

Britain also contributes to global weather predictions through its membership of the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT). Predicting the course of potentially hazardous weather conditions is of obvious global benefit, and satellite observations play an important part in plotting their development,

as well as contributing to our longer-term knowledge of how our climate is changing. EUMETSAT collaborates with other space-faring nations to produce a global view of meteorological conditions worldwide. The UK is represented at EUMETSAT by the Meteorological Office.

Other International Collaborations

The UK has other alliances outside Europe. As with ESA, the UK seeks to pool resources and expertise with other nations to further the space interests of all involved. For example, two of the small satellite projects that have been awarded BNSC funds through its MOSAIC programme have been collaborations with Nigeria. Britain is also in exploratory discussion with Japan on future Earth observation projects, and within the NASA Space Science programme, the UK space industry is working on the STEREO, SWIFT, and Solar-B projects.

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SATELLITE NAVIGATION

Plans for a European civilian satellite navigation system were finally agreed by European Union Transport Ministers on 26th March 2002. The approval of the development phase of the Galileo project is a major step towards closer working between ESA and the EU, and has the potential to create many jobs across Europe and to benefit people throughout the world.

As mobile technology enters more areas of everyday life, the benefits of knowing one's exact position become even more obvious. The new European Galileo system of civilian satellite navigation, which will be able to pinpoint an individual's position with unprecedented accuracy, will be of vital importance to European society, and internationally.

Although the US Global Positioning System (GPS) and Glonass, the Russian system, have been in operation for some time, they were originally designed for military purposes, and come with no

performance guarantees. Galileo will work alongside these two systems to provide a continuity of service with navigation signals accurate and reliable enough to be used in 'safety of life' applications, such as air traffic control, road, rail and maritime navigation, even helping in 'search and rescue' operations, or ambulance tracking for major incident control. It is designed to be operational from 2008.

ESA's objectives when drawing up its original plans for Galileo were far-reaching. The system should have the capacity to provide the services required

by its users and the development of the system had to be carried out cost-effectively, using management techniques borne out of the private sector. Galileo also signifies an important boost for British and European industry, as the system requires the development of many advanced technologies to support the satellite network, its ground support system, and the many downstream applications that it will foster. The UK strongly supports these objectives and looks to play a major part in the development of Galileo.

In fact, work on these applications started several years ago, as Europe has been refining the GPS data available today using the European Global Navigation Overlay Service or EGNOS, the precursor of Galileo,

due to enter service in 2004. EGNOS is Europe's first generation navigation system, complementing existing US and Japanese systems to provide a global service to users. It offers improved performance whilst reducing Europe's dependence on the current terrestrial systems which are expensive to maintain and replace.

The next stage in Galileo's progress to market is due to occur at the end of 2003, when the services it will offer and the management system governing its operations are expected to be finalised.

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1-3. The Galileo satellite navigation system will foster many exciting, downstream applications, such as intelligent transport systems, precision agricultural processes, as well as countless consumer benefits (Images: ESA).

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SATELLITE COMMUNICATIONS

BNSC is closely involved with developments in the UK satellite communications industry, one of the most dynamic industries of our time. Through its three year S@TCOM programme, BNSC is supporting studies and bringing many projects in this field to market both in the UK and internationally.

Telecommunications and broadcasting are the most profitable applications of space technology in the UK. BNSC's survey of the size and health of the UK space industry 2001 showed that this sector represents 78 per cent of all UK space industry turnover, and this figure does not include all the 'direct to home' satellite services that are currently being provided. Taking such services into account, the satellite communication service providers produced a total turnover of £1.9 billion in 2000/2001, representing a growth of 19.1 per cent over the previous year.

1. The satellite telecommunications sector is growing at a rapid pace. This is Artemis, ESA's latest telecommunications satellite, which was launched in July 2001 (Image: ESA).

Most businesses in this sector are optimistic that growth is set to continue, and forecasts predict the industry worldwide will have grown to \$140 billion per annum by 2010. The convergence of technology in the IT, broadband, multimedia, mobile and digital broadcasting sectors will ultimately present even more exciting opportunities in the form of fast and affordable telecommunication services to communities worldwide. BNSC aims to encourage UK industry to exploit these opportunities.

BNSC's own S@TCOM national programme, the first round of

which was launched in February 2000, is helping UK companies develop innovative technology and applications that are designed to compete in an increasingly electronic and mobile environment. S@TCOM awarded funds to 16 UK projects and studies in its second round in July 2001. The third round was launched in February 2002 and the successful applicants will be announced later in 2002.

Central to BNSC are the ESA programmes that have been formulated to encourage growth in this sector. At the ESA Ministerial Council, held in

November 2001, the UK announced an increased contribution to ESA's Advanced Research in Telecommunications Systems (ARTES) programme. The ARTES 3 programme assists small and medium-sized companies to bring innovative satellite-based concepts to market, focusing on multimedia and information infrastructures, and BNSC will be inviting UK companies to apply for the next round of these awards during the coming year. BNSC also supports ESA's ARTES 1 programme (basic studies and investigations), and ARTES 4 programme (ESA/industry

BROADBAND FOR THE FARMING COMMUNITY

Satellite technology offers a much-needed solution to those living in non-metropolitan areas, who are unlikely to be offered the choice of high speed Internet service provision via cable or ADSL that is available in major towns. In 2001, UK company Avanti Communications, with the financial support of BNSC's S@TCOM programme, undertook a major project, called 'Rural Internet Access' to test the

viability of delivering broadband internet access by satellite to rural users. During the trial, Avanti provided a number of rich multimedia services as well as Internet access, in order to demonstrate the power of satellite. The trial proved that demand was strong for the services among the rural community.

As a direct result of this work, Avanti successfully raised capital from a syndicate of private investors in January 2002. This investment has been used to

deploy new satellite transmission infrastructure and launch the 'Amba Broadband' service. Avanti is using this infrastructure to provide Internet access by satellite at speeds of up to 2Mb per second. It now has 100 per cent geographic coverage and therefore can provide a service to any user, anywhere within the UK. The Amba service was initially marketed to large corporate networking customers unable to access terrestrial broadband, but was made more widely available in May 2002.

telecoms partnership programme), from which the UK can benefit, as well as the EU's Framework 5 programme.

Satellite Technology Links Ambulances To Hospitals

Through the ARTES 3 programme, ESYS Ltd and Ortivus (UK) Ltd sought to enable the use of ambulance monitoring systems in remote areas using satellite technology. Mobimed is a mobile patient informatics and monitoring system, which normally uses either radio or GSM cellular technology to relay vital information about the patient travelling in an ambulance to the hospital, so that specialists can monitor the condition of the patient and advise on appropriate action. However, remote areas of the UK do not have full GSM

or radio coverage. The SECoM (Satellite Enhanced Coverage of Mobimed) system, devised by ESYS Ltd, enables the unit to switch automatically to a GlobalStar satellite phone on leaving an area of GSM coverage. Testing of the combined GSM and Globalstar operation of Mobimed was completed successfully in 2001 and the system is now being installed on ambulances in Wales.

For more information on the S@TCOM programme, contact Hemat Gohil
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1. The Artemis satellite undergoing rigorous testing procedures at the ESTEC testing centre in Holland. 2. Artist's impression of Artemis in orbit (Images: ESA).

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DEVELOPING NEW TECHNOLOGY

With the encouragement and support of BNSC, there are many exciting innovations in new technology in the UK. They are being developed in order to meet the needs of future space missions and to further the capabilities of the industry. By working together, British scientists and engineers are helping to make space technology more cost effective and helping to transfer these technologies into other industries.

The technologies that are continually being developed by the space industries are at the forefront of technical innovation. It is important that these developments are co-ordinated so that, as far as possible, knowledge can be shared not only within the space industry, but also with other industries. Thus, the advances made can meet future requirements and be exploited to maximum effect.

BNSC's own survey into the size and health of the UK space industry 2001, showed that the industry continues to grow in terms of both turnover and employment, with telecommunications, broadcasting and Earth observation the most important application

sectors. The UK and European space industries are currently going through a degree of reorganisation to become even more closely aligned with the needs of future space missions and international competitive telecommunication projects.

While reorganisation is in the domain of the heavyweights in the space industry, the vast majority of firms working in this field are small or medium-sized companies (SMEs). Both BNSC and ESA are encouraging SMEs through special initiatives, which will assist them to work together and with larger companies. For instance, more than 50 organisations banded together to present the 18 proposals

submitted to the BNSC in response to its MOSAIC programme (Micro Satellite Applications in Collaboration). MOSAIC was launched in 2000 in order to build on the UK's world-leading expertise in small satellite technologies, which are driving down the cost of access to space for users worldwide. Three of the projects that were originally submitted have gone into development.

One of these, the TopSat project, will see its satellite launched in 2004. UK organisation QinetiQ is leading the consortium of companies that has been involved in TopSat's development, which will provide high-resolution imagery direct to local users from a low-cost satellite. A second project, the Disaster Monitoring Constellation or DMC, led by Surrey Satellite Technology Ltd (SSTL), will allow daily imaging from space via a network of affordable micro-satellites. DMC is currently due for launch in 2003. The third scheme, the Gemini low cost geostationary telecommunications satellite project, in which SSTL is collaborating with Nigeria, is also underway.

The uses for tiny satellite technology continue to grow. For instance, SSTL's first nano-satellite, SNAP-1, which was launched in 2001, weighs just six kilograms. SNAP-1 has advanced Global Positioning System (GPS) navigation control technologies, all developed in the UK, and is used to inspect other spacecraft in orbit. The tiny space GPS receiver has been further developed for use on the Enterprise Module of the International Space Station.

BNSC's National Technology Programme, which aims to stimulate leading edge generic technology for the

future, has invested over the last year in the development of micro and nano technology (or MNT). The space applications of MNT could substantially reduce the size of satellite subsystems, so that they are cheaper to launch, and can be used in large numbers to create a 'swarm' effect, that could have a myriad of observational uses in space, as well as on the ground. BNSC is co-funding facilities at Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) in Oxford that manufacture and test MNT devices.

For more information on how BNSC is encouraging the development of new technology, contact David Leadbeater

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1-5. The TopSat small satellite project will provide high resolution imagery direct to users at a relatively low cost (Images: QinetiQ).

NEW ARTEMIS SATELLITE SAVED

When ESA's Artemis telecommunications satellite was launched on July 12th 2001, it soon became apparent that the Ariane 5 launcher had propelled it into a transfer orbit far lower than expected. Conventional satellites do not carry enough fuel to compensate for a shortfall of this magnitude. However, Artemis had on-board two ion propulsion systems, one of which was the

Electron Bombardment Ion Thruster Assembly, developed by QinetiQ and manufactured by Astrium UK.

Both these systems were originally designed to 'station-keep' once the satellite was in geostationary orbit. A European team, supported by ESA engineers, carried out a series of recovery manoeuvres to propel Artemis away from dangerous radiation into a safe parking orbit, before using the thrusters to move slowly and carefully into the correct orbit. There will be enough

fuel in the tanks to sustain an operational life of more than five years. Artemis is expected to finally arrive in geostationary orbit later in 2002.

Since the problems of how to dispose safely of satellites that have come to the end of operations, and how to move them to a different location, continue to grow, this innovative use of ion propulsion systems could have wider implications in the future of satellite movement and disposal.

07//12

EARTH OBSERVATION

The first images to be returned from Envisat. 1. Sicily. 2. Envisat images with African topography derived from ERS-2. 3. Phytoplankton along the West Coast of Africa (Images: ESA).

One of the most important events of the year for the European space sector, and for the world at large, was the launch of the most advanced Earth observation satellite ever, Envisat. Launched by the European Space Agency on 1st March 2002, Envisat will undertake a global health check by providing vital information about global warming, climate change and the depletion of the ozone layer.

Envisat, ESA's £1.4 billion Earth observation satellite, was launched from Kourou spaceport in French Guiana in the early hours of 1st March 2002. It was this event that grabbed the headlines but, in fact, the launch of Envisat represented years of planning and collaboration between UK and European scientists and engineers, with the UK playing a major role in its success. Furthermore, the successful launch marks a new era of unprecedented access to Earth observation data for environmental scientists. The highly precise launch that was achieved means that Envisat may be able to continue delivering data back to Earth for even longer than the 5 years anticipated.

For over a decade, scientists and designers across Europe have worked together to design and build the world's largest and most advanced Earth observation satellite. The UK Government has invested £300 million into the programme, and one of the ten main instruments on board the satellite, the Advanced Along Track Scanning Radiometer (AATSR), was funded and developed as a UK national project.

Twelve UK firms were closely involved in the development and construction of Envisat. For instance, Astrium UK, as prime contractor, coordinated the input of over 100 companies across Europe.

As well as providing new observations of our land, atmosphere, ice caps and oceans, Envisat will complete a 15 year dataset of valuable observations of our changing environment. Such observations continue the legacy of the ERS-1 and 2 satellites, which, for example, have provided information on the changing temperatures of our seas – a valuable indicator of climate change. Envisat takes just 100 minutes to circle the Earth, monitoring the oceans, ice caps, vegetation and the atmosphere as it goes. It has already returned its first images, although it will not be fully operational until September 2002. Once operational, the regular, consistent observations returned to Earth will enable scientists to detect minute changes occurring on Earth, providing support to future environmental policies.

Supporting Global Aims

Envisat data will make key contributions to the European initiative for Global Monitoring for Environment and Security (GMES). This initiative,

which gained a strong commitment from ESA's Ministerial Council in November 2001, is set to come into effect by 2008. It focuses on improving the ways that Europe uses its Earth observation systems to help us manage our natural resources in the most effective way.

ESA's EarthWatch concept is also helping to put in place the processes needed to deliver GMES requirements. In response to a call for ideas from the EarthWatch programme, the Infoterra/TerraSAR initiative was formed. The main goal of this initiative is to establish a self-sustaining, geo-information business built on European strengths in synthetic aperture radar (SAR) satellite technology, and SAR application expertise. TerraSAR data will be utilised in many diverse areas, from precision farming to oil spill monitoring. At the ESA Ministerial Council meeting in November 2001, Member States subscribed 25 Meuros for advanced technical work to take the concept forward.

ESA is also committed to continuing its scientific investigations under the banner of its Earth Explorer programme. There are two types of Earth Explorer mission: 'Core' and 'Opportunity'. Core missions respond directly to scientific issues which address specific areas of public concern. The first mission, scheduled for launch in early 2005, is GOCE (Gravity Field and Steady-State Ocean Circulation Mission). This has considerable UK involvement, and will study the Earth's gravity field and ocean circulation. All three of the currently proposed projects for the next phase of the Explorer programme have significant UK interest.

The first two scheduled Opportunity Missions, which use smaller, low-cost satellites focused on particular scientific processes, also have strong UK involvement. The first Opportunity Mission, CryoSat, is led by the UK. It is due to be launched in 2004 and will determine variations in the thickness of the Earth's continental ice sheets and marine ice cover. Its primary aim is to test whether sea ice is thinning due to global warming, by providing climate researchers with data that has never been retrieved from these uninhabited regions. Changes in sea ice thickness are a highly sensitive indicator of climate change globally.

UK Expertise

The UK's strengths in the science and technology that underpin remote sensing mean that British organisations are at the forefront of Earth observation projects. In 2001, BNSC, keen that the UK continues to play a major role in the future, introduced the Newton (New Technologies for Observational Needs) programme. This is designed to improve the UK's industrial capability in this field, as well as to maximize the economic benefits achieved from the development of Earth observation technology. It fosters partnerships between engineers and scientists in the UK space sector and internationally, in order to ensure that the technology of the future will meet the scientific requirements of the time.

Through the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), BNSC is also active in supporting collaborative research between academia and industry through its Earth observation LINK programme. This is a programme

1. Envisat at the ESTEC testing centre, prior to launch. 2-3. Envisat soared into orbit on 1st March, 2002 (Images: ESA).

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aimed at supporting pre-competitive research, aligning scientific expertise to industrial needs. Projects that have been funded through the LINK programme will bring many benefits to various communities around the world. For example, the RADWHEAT Project is helping farmers maximize their yields by monitoring crop health using high resolution 3-D radar images.

In order to continue encouraging the highest standards in UK Earth observation, NERC has established two new Centres of Excellence, with a total investment of around £4 million. The Centre for Terrestrial Carbon Dynamics, based at the University of Sheffield, brings together experts who will use information from space to find out more about the contribution of carbon that is tied up in our ecosystems to the global carbon cycle, and hence global warming. The Centre for Observation and Modelling of Earthquakes and Tectonics (or COMET), based at the University of Oxford, uses new satellite techniques to measure movements in the Earth's crust to formulate models that will help forecast earthquakes. In September 2002, NERC will be inviting another round of ideas for new Centres of Excellence.

OBSERVING THE WEATHER FROM SPACE

Satellite pictures on our weather forecasts are one of the most high profile uses for Earth observation imagery. The Met Office works with many different representatives from the international space industry in order to ensure that there are relevant data available for our needs, both now and in the future, and that this data is obtained as cost-effectively as possible.

The Met Office also represents the UK at the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT). EUMETSAT, in conjunction with ESA, is planning the launch of an important new meteorological satellite called Meteosat Second Generation (MSG). This will improve our short term weather forecasts considerably, and is due for launch in August 2002.

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1. Artist's impression of Envisat in orbit (Image: ESA) 2. Sea level and temperature will be measured by the Radar Altimeter and AATSR on board Envisat (Image: ESA).

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SPACE SCIENCE

BNSC is committed to promoting excellence in space science research. UK funds are allocated to ESA and other international space science missions through the Particle Physics and Astronomy Research Council (PPARC).

Both the science community and the public at large have long been fascinated by space.

As well as satisfying mankind's natural curiosity, the UK's investment in space science also improves the nation's prosperity by increasing our knowledge base and indirectly fuelling other more commercial sectors. Furthermore, once the technical challenges involved in the planning of space science missions have been met, the knowledge that is gained can

often be transferred to wealth-creating industries, such as telecommunications and satellite navigation.

We are now at an exciting stage in our discoveries about the universe and our place within it, and the UK is playing an integral part in this. A large proportion of the UK's space science budget funds ESA missions, in which British scientists and engineers have a close involvement.

For instance, three of the eleven instruments carried by each of the four identical satellites making up the Cluster mission, to study the Sun's effects on the Earth, were led by British research teams. The UK also provides the Cluster Science Operations Centre. The Cluster quartet sent back significant data in November 2001 when matter ejected from the Sun collided with the Earth's magnetic field, exposing the Cluster satellites to the full blast of the supersonic solar wind. The Cluster instruments provided evidence of the effects of the blast on the boundary

three of the eleven instruments carried by each of the four identical satellites making up the Cluster mission, were led by British research teams

of the magnetic field – the magnetopause. These results will eventually help us to predict how such dramatic changes could affect Earth in the future.

Another set of exciting results has come from ESA's XMM-Newton spacecraft, the most sensitive X-ray observatory ever to fly in space. Newton, observing a spiral galaxy 100 million light years from Earth, found that its central black hole, rather than behaving as expected by simply pulling all energy into it, seemed to be allowing energy to escape. An international team of astronomers found a surprisingly strong X-ray emission from the galactic centre, which, they believe, must be energy escaping from the black hole.

Meanwhile, the ESA Huygens probe, carried by the NASA Cassini spacecraft, continues on its seven year

1. One of the four Cluster satellites flying in formation to study the Sun's effects on the Earth. 2. XMM-Newton is providing scientists with dramatic observations of supernovae as in this artist's impression. 3. ESA's Huygens probe, carried by NASA's Cassini spacecraft (Images: ESA).

journey to Saturn where it is due to arrive in 2004, in order to investigate its rings and its magnetosphere, as well as the planet's smaller icy moons. Huygens will land on the surface of Saturn's moon, Titan. UK industry helped develop the Huygens flight software, the descent system and the parachutes, while UK scientists have worked on the development of eight of the 18 instruments on Huygens and Cassini.

The British Beagle 2 Lander will be the next craft to land on Mars, in December 2003, as part of ESA's Mars Express mission. Beagle 2 will explore whether conditions for life on Mars exist or ever have existed. A unique academia-industry team in the UK, led by the Open University and Astrium plc, has developed the lander.

The British Beagle 2 Lander (above) will be the next craft to land on Mars, in December 2003, as part of ESA's Mars Express mission

In January 2003, the ESA Rosetta mission will start its 8-year journey to Comet Wirtanen. The mission will include landing on the comet and key measurements of the composition of the surface and sub-surface will be made by the UK instrument, Ptolemy, recently completed and delivered by the Open University. Launch of Rosetta will be followed within a month by launch of the ESA SMART-1 mission to the Moon. On SMART-1 the prime science instrument is D-CIXS, shortly to be delivered to ESA by the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL). D-CIXS will, for the first time, determine the global composition of the lunar surface in order to test theories of the origins of the Moon.

Outside Europe

Although the majority of the UK's space science budget is channelled via ESA, Britain is also taking part in important missions conducted by NASA. For example, the SWIFT mission to study Gamma Ray Bursts is due for launch in Autumn 2003, and

scientists from Leicester University and the Mullard Space Laboratory of University College London are part of its international team. The UK is providing two of the three specialist telescopes on the spacecraft.

UK funding has also been provided to enable scientists at Birmingham University and Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) to provide the Heliospheric Imager instrument for NASA's small explorer mission, the Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory (STEREO). STEREO will consist of two spacecraft, observing the coronal mass ejections, the eruptions on the Sun that eject matter into space, and the consequent interaction of that matter with the Earth.

Solar-B is a joint UK/US/Japan mission to be launched in August 2005. This solar optical telescope will be placed in a Sun-synchronous orbit at an altitude of 600 km, allowing long-term solar viewing for eight months each year (short eclipses limit viewing for four months of the year) helping us to understand the relationship between the solar photosphere, the thick glowing gas which represents the surface of the sun, and the corona, the thinner gas that extends millions of kilometres into space. The UK is building a number of components for Solar-B's Imaging Spectrometer.

The Future of Solar System Exploration

The UK is also taking an active role in the long-term planning of the future of space exploration. ESA's Aurora Programme is planning for this future, looking at how existing technologies need to be developed and gaps in Europe's expertise need to be filled, to set realistic technological goals for the next 30

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years of space exploration. Aurora is expected to include development of autonomous, intelligent robotics to return samples to Earth from Mars and asteroids, with the longer-term objective of investigating possibilities for human exploration of the solar system. Over the next three years, the Aurora team, which includes British representatives, will consider more than 300 European ideas to bring these possibilities to fruition in order to develop a proposal for a full programme.

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2. ESA's SMART-1 mission, to be launched in February 2003, is to revisit the moon. 3. XMM-Newton has provided surprising information about the nature of black holes (Images: ESA).

The question of whether there is life on other planets continues to fascinate scientists and the general public. Britain's contribution to this field, which is known as Astrobiology, is important, as its high levels of technical innovation in instrument design and its strengths in biochemistry, molecular biology, evolutionary biology, planetary geology and geophysics are being pooled in order to progress the debate through further evidence. The UK Astrobiology Network has been formed to aid communication between active researchers in this field (visit www.astrobiology.rl.ac.uk for more information).

For more information about the UK's Space Science programme, contact Dave Hall

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PUBLICITY AND EDUCATION

One of BNSC's primary objectives is to inform the general public about the UK's activities in space. It achieves this through an active Publicity and Education Unit, which works closely with the press, the space industry, schools and colleges, on a wide variety of projects.

1-2. BNSC's Learning Zone was relaunched at the Education Shows early in 2002. New sections provide comprehensive information for schools and colleges on the Solar System and Earth observation, in line with the National Curriculum.

BNSC is committed to communicating the results of the UK's space projects, and their significance to our everyday lives, to a broad audience, alongside actively promoting the UK space industry. Through the work of its Publicity and Education Unit, BNSC is reaching more people than ever before.

The BNSC website is a major source of space related information, for both the general public and industry or academic specialists.

BNSC attends a number of major exhibitions throughout the year. For example, at the Tomorrow's World Live exhibition, held in July 2001, BNSC staged a Live Lab that gave daily presentations to highlight issues such as the importance of Earth observation in environmental monitoring. At this event, with support from ESA, BNSC ran a competition to win a trip to Kourou Spaceport to see the launch of the Envisat Earth observation satellite. Early in 2002, BNSC also attended the Education Shows held in Glasgow and Birmingham, where it demonstrated to teachers and lecturers the many ways that its resources can enrich space-based educational activities.

The 2002 Education Shows were also the setting for the relaunch of BNSC's web-based Learning Zone, a specialist site packed with information for students and teachers, including sample lesson plans, interactive games and activities. Two new, expanded sections were introduced dealing

with the planet Earth and the Solar System.

The BNSC website is a major source of space related information, for both the general public and industry or academic specialists. Following recent improvements to the site earlier this year, there is now an updated version of the UK Space Directory available on-line, in addition to the newly launched image bank, Envisat showcase, and Earth Observation industry showcase.

BNSC also works hard to focus the public's attention on important events in the space calendar. In November 2001, it held a series of events in Scotland to coincide with ESA's Ministerial Council meeting. BNSC staged events at the Dynamic Earth centre, and an exhibition at Glasgow's City Art Gallery. Similarly, at the launch of the world's largest Earth observation satellite, Envisat, in March 2002, BNSC co-ordinated with the British media to bring the story alive through interviews with scientists and engineers.

BNSC staged a special breakfast event at the Science Museum in London, and via a satellite link, young adults at the National Space Science Centre in Leicester questioned scientists about Envisat.

Another highlight of the past year was the continuing success of BNSC's CD-Rom series entitled 'Window On...'. Started in September 1998 with 'Window On The World', a CD-Rom that went out with 1.5 million copies of The Sunday Times, the series continued with the 'Window On The UK 2000' CD. Then, in September 2001, BNSC, in collaboration with the Particle Physics and Astronomy Research Council and other partners, produced two CD-Roms entitled 'Window On The Universe', containing over 500 zoomable images and specialist articles. BNSC has now supplied over five million of its educational CD-Roms to the public, significantly raising public awareness of space.

BNSC is now looking forward to the next year's activities in publicity and education. It will be hosting a stand with ESA at the Farnborough International Airshow 2002 exhibition on 22nd-28th July,

PUBLICATIONS AND WEBSITES

1. BSNC's website

(www.bnsc.gov.uk) is the location of information related to the UK's space activities. In addition, BNSC has an expanding series of publications aimed at different sections of the space community and the public:

2. UK Space Directory

A directory of the UK space industry and related establishments

3. Space UK

A free termly magazine for students and enthusiasts

4. UK Space Strategy 1999-2002

This document gives an in-depth view of the UK's space policy

5. BNSC Leaflets

The following subject areas are available free:

- Introduction to BNSC
- Careers in Space
- Telecommunications
- Satellite Navigation
- Space Debris
- Near Earth Objects
- Technology
- BNSC in Europe
- Microgravity
- Space Science
- UK Space Industry and Exports
- Earth Observation Principles
- Earth Observation Applications
- The MOSAIC Small Satellite Programme
- Envisat

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where it will be showing how the many applications of space technology can be used to protect the Earth and improve communications and navigation. Here, BNSC will launch a new BNSC interactive video, which has been produced by the Publicity and Education department in order to highlight the diversity of its space activities and the benefits they bring to the public. Also at the Farnborough International Airshow, BNSC will be launching the new paper copy of its UK Space Directory, a comprehensive list of all the companies, research institutions and academic departments that are involved in the UK space industry and its offshoots.

Later in the year, BNSC will be exhibiting at the World Space Congress in Houston, Texas in October 2002. This event, held every 10 years, is an ideal opportunity for BNSC to present its activities on the world stage.

For more information about BNSC's Publicity and Educational activities, contact Steve Warren

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LIFE AND PHYSICAL SCIENCES

BNSC plays an active part in ESA's Microgravity programme, which studies many processes in the Life and Physical Sciences by removing the effects of the gravitational pull felt on Earth. UK scientists continue to carry out some amazing research in the weightless environment of space. The benefits of this research are widespread across many industries.

The ability to conduct experiments in space opens up many possibilities for scientific research. In space laboratories such as the International Space Station, researchers make use of the weightless conditions, as well as the radiation environment and extreme vacuum, to make breakthroughs in the fields of new medical and industrial techniques, and environmental

technologies. Excellent scientific discoveries are being made in the areas of combustions, genomics, proteins, plasmas, medicine, exobiology and atmospheric pollution. Although the UK does not currently take part in experiments on the International Space Station, BNSC has a unique and beneficial role to play in the future of the UK's involvement in

BNSC has a unique and beneficial role to play in the future of the UK's involvement in microgravity experiments

microgravity experiments. Such research is at the early stages of its development, and BNSC is currently investigating the cost effectiveness and possible benefits of participation. As part of this consideration, the UK is taking part in ESA's Microgravity programme EMIR-2X.

In addition, groups of UK scientists are undertaking various projects and studies into the use of microgravity in an industrial context. One project, which has received funding from both ESA and DTI, involves the study of the thermophysical properties of metals. This research is helping scientists understand the properties of molten metals. The results could lead to many benefits in the casting of components that are very large, made of unusual alloys or with unusual properties.

New Microgravity Programme

At ESA's Ministerial Council, held in Edinburgh in November 2001, Ministers approved the first stage of the new ELIPS programme, the European programme for life and physical sciences and applications utilising the International Space Station. Its objective is to maximise the benefits to society that can be gained from using the International Space Station, and to set up a framework for European activity in microgravity experiments.

For more information on Life and Physical Sciences, contact Jeremy Curtis
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1-2. The UK is currently considering its future involvement in experimentation in space.

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NEAR EARTH OBJECTS

The Task Force set up to investigate how the UK could assist the international response to the threat posed to the world by Near Earth Objects, presented its report to Government in September 2000. Since then, BNSC, along with other Government departments, has worked hard to put into place many of the commitments made by Government in response to the report.

In addition, through its membership of international bodies, the UK is helping to formulate a global solution to what is undoubtedly an international issue. The potential threat of an impact from a Near Earth Object, or NEO, is being taken seriously. In February 2000, Lord Sainsbury set up a Task Force to investigate the extent of

the hazard, and its report was published later that year. In response to this report, the Government set up a new intergovernmental team to put its recommendations into place.

An update of the progress of this team was issued in January 2002. One of its most significant actions was the opening of the NEO

Information Centre, in April 2002, at the UK National Space Science Centre at Leicester, supported by the National History Museum, W5 in Belfast and the UK Astronomy Technology Centre in Edinburgh. In addition, academic support is available from a range of Universities including Queen Mary (London), Queens (Belfast),

WHAT IS A NEAR EARTH OBJECT?

A Near Earth Object or NEO is an asteroid or a comet that is in an orbit that brings it close to Earth. Generally, NEOs are pronounced potentially hazardous when they come within 0.05 Astronomical Unit (AU) of Earth (7.5 million kilometres, or about 20 times the distance between Earth and the Moon), and when they are at least 150 metres in diameter.

There are countless asteroids and comets in the Solar System, but only a tiny fraction of these are classified as NEOs. Latest estimates suggest that there are roughly 150 million ten metre objects, some 300,000 one hundred metre objects, about 10,000 five hundred metre objects and perhaps 1,500 which are one kilometre or larger.

For more information on Near Earth Objects, contact
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Tel: 020 7215 0821
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1. Meteor Crater in Arizona (Image: NASA).
2. Artist's impression of a catastrophic asteroid impact with early Earth (Image: NASA).

Leicester and the Open University. The Centre will work with BNSC and the space community, acting as a hub for all NEO activity in the UK. As well as keeping the public abreast of developments, the Centre will provide a focus for future research.

The Particle Physics and Astronomy Research Council (PPARC) has also commissioned a review of the facilities presently available to the UK for identifying and tracking hazardous NEOs. Observing time has been made available for further investigation of the possibilities. The study is leading to several new initiatives in astronomy.

International Collaborations

Naturally, the possible dangers posed by Near Earth Objects affect every country. Therefore, an international approach to the problem is the best way to tackle it. The Government is working with many other nations and a wide range of international organisations to establish a strategy to tackle the issue, as well as leading an international forum for discussion and action on NEOs.

For example, Dr Paul Murdin (formerly BNSC Director of Space Science) is chairing the steering committee to study the issue at the OECD Global Science Forum (GSF). The Committee will be holding a workshop at the NEO Information Centre in the UK in September 2002, from which it will be formulating a list of recommendations for future action, to be submitted to the GSF in January 2003.

The UK also leads the UN Action Team, which aims to carry forward the recommendation from the Vienna Declaration of the Unispace III UN World Space Conference to improve the international co-ordination of activities related to NEOs. The Action Team met in February 2002 and will be circulating agreed actions to other nations during this year.

A special website gives more details, visit:
www.nearearthobjects.co.uk

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THE OUTER SPACE ACT

The Outer Space Act 1986 is the UK's regulatory framework for activities in space.

It ensures that all activities in space carried out by UK nationals, comply with our obligations under international treaties and conventions by asking companies to apply for a licence from BNSC whenever they are carrying out one of the following activities:

- Launching or procuring the launch of a space object
- Operating a space object
- Any other activity in outer space

Before granting a licence to a company, the Secretary of State has to be satisfied that the activity will not jeopardise public health or the safety of persons or property; will be consistent with the international obligations of the UK; and will not impair national security. Applicants also have to produce adequate third party insurance covering their activity. In addition, the policies should name Her Majesty's Government

in the UK as an Additional Insured. BNSC aims to provide a clear and transparent licensing regime, giving a stable and predictable operating environment for participants in space activities. Since 1989, BNSC has granted 23 licences to applicants under the Act and advised Governors of UK Overseas Territories on nine applications. The process of applying for a licence is relatively simple. Applications must be submitted six months ahead of launch, or of assuming operational control of a satellite, accompanied by a cheque for £6,500. Business is also required to pay any insurance premium.

For more information about The Outer Space Act visit the regulatory section of the BNSC website at: www.bnsc.gov.uk

March 2001 saw the re-entry of the Mir space station to Earth's atmosphere. The safe disposal of satellites is an important consideration for space users (Images: courtesy of Analytical Graphics Inc.).

BNSC co-ordinates how the UK's civil space budget is spent by its funding partners. Partners' expenditure is directed to meeting their own objectives and BNSC seeks to exploit synergies to ensure the maximum collective benefit, in line with the UK Space Strategy. Around 60 per cent of UK space funding goes into the European Space Agency to finance projects such as Envisat, Galileo and Mars Express.

CIVIL SPACE EXPENDITURE CO-ORDINATED THROUGH BNSC

1. Source of funds (£ million)

	1995/96	1996/97	1997/98	1998/99	1999/00	2000/01	2001/02
DTI	99.87	103.80	102.68	87.76	87.73	80.89	87.60
PPARC	61.38	51.10	42.76	38.71	38.98	41.30	42.60
Met. Office	20.54	23.90	15.05	23.16	27.11	24.06	23.27
NERC	12.30	11.90	12.70	11.10	11.00	11.00	10.60
MOD	7.82	7.42	7.06	6.82	6.35	6.11	5.00
Dept. for Transport*	0.00	1.04	1.04	16.04	1.04	3.60	0.41
DEFRA **	2.98	2.25	1.90	1.40	0.43	0.62	-
TOTAL	194.89	201.41	183.18	184.99	172.62	177.38	169.18

* (formerly part of the Department of Transport, Local Government and the Regions)

** (formerly part of Department of Environment, Transport & the Regions and Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food)

CIVIL SPACE EXPENDITURE CO-ORDINATED THROUGH BNSC

2. Break down of funds – By subject and spend area (£ million)

	1995/96	1996/97	1997/98	1998/99	1999/00	2000/01	2001/02
Earth Observation							
National	45.80	47.70	34.69	41.10	44.68	41.12	40.02
ESA	48.58	58.90	60.81	58.74	44.23	26.03	28.18
Science/Microgravity							
National	13.21	11.50	9.50	7.50	9.56	12.00	13.10
ESA	39.32	41.90	33.81	32.95	32.29	33.42	28.65
Telecommunications							
National	4.00	3.50	4.00	3.80	3.70	7.55	8.71
ESA	16.76	12.30	10.40	5.58	7.88	22.09	19.75
Technology							
National	0.31	1.11	1.15	2.38	7.04	18.00	8.63
ESA	2.26	2.20	2.66	0.00	4.83	0.75	
Transportation							
National	0.11	0.20	0.28	0.17	0.26	0.39	
ESA	7.43	4.40	4.79	18.59*	4.53	4.04	4.00
Other National	0.26	0.30	0.31	0.22	0.30	0.32	1.59
ESA General Budget	16.85	17.40	20.98	13.96	13.52	11.67	16.55
TOTAL	194.89	201.41	183.18	184.99	172.62	177.38	169.18

*1998/99 figures include National Air Traffic Service's contribution of £15 million to ESA's EGNOS(GNSS-1) Programme

USEFUL CONTACTS

Here are contact details for some of BNSC's partners, along with other useful addresses where you can find out more about space activities in the UK.

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QinetiQ

Customer Contact Team
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United Kingdom
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Fax: +44 (0) 1252 393399
www.QinetiQ.com
email: CUSTOMERCONTACT@QinetiQ.com

Meteorological Office

London Road
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Berkshire RG12 2SZ
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Fax: +44 (0) 1344 854160
www.met-office.gov.uk
email: mvjones@meto.gov.uk

NERC – Natural Environment Research Council

Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon
Wiltshire SN2 1EU
Tel: +44 (0) 1793 411781
Fax: +44 (0) 1793 411545
www.nerc.ac.uk
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PPARC – Particle Physics and Astronomy Research Council

Polaris House
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RAL – Rutherford Appleton Laboratory

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UKISC Member Organisations

Astrium, British Aerospace Defence Systems,
British Telecommunications, ComDev Europe,
ERA Technology, ESYS, IGG Component
Technology, InfoTerra Ltd, Logica, Martin Baker,
Pilkington Optronics Space Technology,
Raytheon Systems Ltd, Science Systems (Space),
Sira Electro-Optics, Systems Engineering and
Assessment Ltd (SEA), Thales Research,
Thorn Security, Vega Group plc

Front cover images show: Envisat launch,
Artemis Communication Satellite, SPOT-4,
SMART-1 (All images courtesy of ESA).

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